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Research Article

FREQUENCY OF PRIMIGRAVIDAS PRESENTING IN LABOUR AT TERM WITH UNDIAGNOSED BREECH AND ITS PERINATAL OUTCOME

¹Dr. Taila Amber, ²Dr. Asma Qayyum, ³Dr. Sadaf Zahra

¹(MBBS, FCPS Obs & Gynae), Senior Registrar Lady Willingdon Hospital, King Edward Medical University, Email: bctkemcol@yahoo.com

² Senior Registrar Fatima Memorial Hospital Lahore, Email: drasma1983@gmail.com

³ Senior Registrar Lady Willingdon Hospital, King Edward Medical University, Email: sadafzahrascorpio@gmail.com

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the frequency of undiagnosed breech and its perinatal outcome in primigravidas presenting in labour.

Setting: Gynecology and obstetrics, Lady Willingdon Hospital, Unit 2, Lahore

Study Design: Descriptive case series

Duration: Study was completed in 6 months after the approval of synopsis (5th March 2014 till 5th September 2014).

Methods: After the approval of the study by the ethical committee of the Lady Willingdon Hospital and informed consent, the cases fulfilling the inclusion criteria was registered. Demographic variables were noted. Whether the breech pregnancy was diagnosed antenatally or undiagnosed was established. Short term neonatal outcomes in terms of Apgar score (at 5 minutes), birth asphyxia, birth injury and admission to neonatal intensive care was noted. All this information was recorded in a pre-designed performa. Data entry and analysis was done by using SPSS 20.

Results: Mean age of the patients was 24.14±2.48 years. There were 195(78%) patients with undiagnosed breech and 55 patients were diagnosed for breech. There were only 10(5.1%) neonates with poor APGAR score. There was only 1(0.5%) neonate who was admitted to NICU. There is no significant association between Poor APGAR score and admission to NICU with age group of the patients. There were 10 neonates who had poor APGAR score at 5 minutes, mothers of all these neonates were presented as undiagnosed breech. No significant association was present between poor APGAR score and undiagnosed breech presentation. No significant association between undiagnosed breech and neonate admission to NICU.

Conclusion: As per findings of this study high frequency of undiagnosed breech before admission was seen in primigravid as before admission. i.e. 195/250 (78%). However prenatal outcome showed that poor APGAR score at 5 minute was seen in 10(5.1%) neonates and only 1(0.5%) neonate was admitted to NICU. These result can help us to diagnose breech before admission in primigravidas before presenting for their delivery so that timely and accurate decision can be made regarding mode of delivery as well as better perinatal outcome.

Key Words: Undiagnosed breech, Perinatal outcome, Primigravidas, Labour

Corresponding author:

Dr. Taila Amber,

(MBBS, FCPS Obs & Gynae), Senior Registrar Lady Willingdon Hospital,
King Edward Medical University,

Email: bctkemcol@yahoo.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Breech presentation occurs in 3-4 % of all deliveries.¹ Traditional belief has always emphasized the importance of detecting a breech presentation during the antenatal course so that the mode of delivery could be better selected. In reality, not all breeches can be diagnosed antenatally. The incidence of breech presentation diagnosed after the onset of labour varies from 21% to 33%.² It is still a common practice in our country that unbooked cases having not being seen by any qualified health person throughout pregnancy present in labour with breech presentation.³ It is commonly assumed that undiagnosed breech in labour is at higher risk of complication than those that have been diagnosed pre-labour and adequately assessed for suitability for trial of vaginal delivery. Undiagnosed breech are more likely to deliver vaginally when presented in advanced labour, with no opportunity of prior assessment for suitability for vaginal breech delivery.⁴ The management of term delivery of fetus in breech presentation is one of the most disputable issues in modern obstetric practice. Several years ago, one of the biggest randomized controlled studies in obstetrics Hannah and colleague's trial, the Term Breech Trial (TBT), tried to set up guidelines and resolve the question

of the best method to deliver the fetus at term in breech presentation.^{4,5}

There are studies which show that undiagnosed breeches may not be as important as they are more likely to deliver vaginally, with no excess morbidity or mortality. There are centers where caesarean sections are performed for all undiagnosed breeches. In a study conducted by Zahoor S et al, out of 203, 163 (80.29%) of women presented in emergency as undiagnosed, while 40 (19.71%) as diagnosed breech. Vaginal delivery was common in undiagnosed group (84.56%) as most of the cases arrived in advanced labour when cesarean section could not be opted for. No baby suffered birth injury and 10 (6.13%) had poor Apgar score in undiagnosed group, and none was admitted to Neonatal intensive care unit.⁶ In another study, it was found that perinatal morbidity was 8.2%.⁷

This study will help in establishing the number of women in their first pregnancy presenting in labour as undiagnosed Breech, and their perinatal outcome so that a local statistical data could be made as I could find only one local study on this issue in the literature.

FIGURE-I: Variations of the Breech Presentation

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This is a Descriptive case series conducted in Gynaecology and obstetrics, Lady Willingdon Hospital, Unit 2, Lahore. Duration of study was 6 months after the approval of synopsis, (5th March 2014 – 5th September 2014). Sampling technique was Non-probability purposive sampling. Sample size was estimated as 250 cases using 95% confidence level, 3% margin of error with an expected percentage of poor Apgar score as 6.13%

SAMPLE SELECTION**INCLUSION CRITERIA**

All term alive breech deliveries presenting in labour, as per operational definitions.

Age of patients : 20-30 years

Parity: Primigravida

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Preterm Breech pregnancies (gestational amenorrhea of <37 weeks as calculated through LMP)

Term infants Patients lost to follow up.

Previous uterine scar i.e. Myomectomy.

Obvious anatomical Congenital anomalies observed after birth of baby.

History of Antepartum hemorrhage affecting mode of delivery.

DATA COLLECTION

After the approval of the study by the ethical committee of the Lady Willingdon Hospital and informed consent, the cases fulfilling the inclusion criteria was registered. Demographic variables were noted. Whether the breech pregnancy was diagnosed antenatally or undiagnosed was established. Short term neonatal outcomes in terms of Apgar score (at 5 minutes), birth asphyxia, birth injury and admission to neonatal intensive care was be noted. All this information was recorded in a pre-designed performa (attached).

DATA ANALYSIS

All the data was entered and analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) 20 version. The qualitative data like undiagnosed breech, types of breech, Poor APGAR score and admission to neonatal intensive care unit, was presented in form of frequency and percentage. The quantitative data like age was presented in the form of mean \pm S.D. Stratification with respect to age and type of breech was done. Post stratification chi-square test was applied. P-value ≤ 0.05 was taken as significant.

RESULTS:

There were total 250 patients in this study. Mean age of the patients was 24.14 ± 2.48 years, the minimum age was 18 years and maximum was 32 years.(Table-1)

All the patients were primigravida in our study 250(100%). (Table-2)

The mean gestational age was 38.46 ± 0.75 weeks. Minimum gestational age was 37 weeks and maximum was 40 weeks.(Table-3)

The mean birth weight of the new born baby was 2.92 ± 0.16 kg. Minimum birth weight was 2.85 kg and maximum birth weight was 3 kg.(Table-4)

There were 195(78%) primigravid as with undiagnosed breech and 55(22%) primigravidas were diagnosed for breech. (Graph-1)

There were only 10(5.1%) neonates with poor APGAR score whereas rest of the neonates 240(94.9%) had normal APGAR score. (Graph-2).

There was only 1(0.5%) neonate who was admitted to NICU. (Graph-3)

There is no significant association between Poor APGAR score and age group of the patients as the p-value is not significant. i.e. (*p-value*=0.94)(Table-5)

There is no significant association between Admission to NICU and age group of the patients as the p-value is not significant. i.e. (*p-value*=0.91)(Table-6)

There were 10 neonates who had poor APGAR score at 5 minutes mothers of all these neonates were presented with undiagnosed breech. While the rest of the 240 neonates 185 mothers presented with undiagnosed breech but they did not have poor APGAR score at 5 minutes. According to p-value no significant association was present between poor APGAR score and undiagnosed breech presentation of mother. i.e. (*p-value*=0.087) (Table-7).

Only 1 neonate was admitted to the NICU and the mother of that neonate was presented with undiagnosed breech however the remaining 249 neonates who were not admitted to NICU among them 194 neonates' mother were presented with undiagnosed breech. P-value showed no significant association between undiagnosed breech and neonate admission to NICU. i.e. (*p-value*-0.595) (Table-8)

**TABLE-1
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR AGE (YEARS)**

N	250
Mean	24.14
Std. Deviation	2.48
Minimum	18
Maximum	32

**TABLE-2
PARITY STATUS OF WOMEN**

	Frequency	Percent
Primigravida	250	100%

**TABLE-3
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR GESTATIONAL AGE (WEEKS)**

N	250
Mean	38.46
Std. Deviation	0.75
Minimum	37
Maximum	40

**TABLE-4
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR BABY BIRTH WEIGHT (KG)**

N	250
Mean	2.92
Std. Deviation	0.160
Minimum	2.85
Maximum	3

**FIGURE-1
UNDIAGNOSED BREECH BEFORE ADMISSION AMONG PATIENTS**

FIGURE-2
POOR APGAR SCORE AT 5 MINUTES (SHORT TERM PERINATAL OUTCOME)

TABLE-5
POOR APGAR SCORE AT 5 MINUTES IN RELATION TO AGE OF MOTHERS

		Poor APGAR Score		Total
		Yes	No	
Age Group	16-20	1(%)	19(7.92%)	20
	21-25	7(%)	153(63.75%)	160
	26-30	2(%)	66(27.50%)	68
	31-35	0(0%)	2(0.83%)	2
Total		10	240	250

Chi-square= 0.39

p-value= 0.94

TABLE-6
ADMISSION TO NICU IN RELATION TO AGE OF MOTHERS

		Admission to NICU		Total
		Yes	No	
Age Group	16-20	0(0%)	20(8.03%)	20
	21-25	1(100%)	159(63.86%)	160
	26-30	0(0%)	68(27.31%)	68
	31-35	0(0%)	2(0.80%)	2
Total		1	249	250

Chi-square=0.57

p-value= 0.91

TABLE-7
POOR APGAR SCORE AT 5 MINUTES IN RELATION TO UNDIAGNOSED BREECH

		Poor APGAR Score		Total
		Yes	No	
Undiagnosed Breech	Yes	10(100%)	185(77.08%)	195
	No	0(0%)	55(22.92%)	55
Total		10	240	250

Chi-square=2.938 *p-value*=0.087

TABLE-8
ADMISSION TO NICU IN RELATION TO UNDIAGNOSED BREECH

		Admission to NICU		Total
		Yes	No	
Undiagnosed Breech	Yes	1(100%)	194(77.91%)	195
	No	0(0%)	55(22.08%)	55
Total		1	249	250

Chi-square=0.283

p-value=0.595

DISCUSSION:

Failure to detect breech presentation has been attributed to many factors including maternal obesity, increased abdominal tone, polyhydramnios, multiple pregnancy, inadequate antenatal care, and obstetric inexperience, although these variables has not been found to be significant in the latest report about undiagnosed breech in the literature.(55)

The vaginal delivery of a term breech is controversial, but recently a meta-analysis of 2 trial sunder aken as part of a Cochrane systemic review found no significant differences between planned vaginal or caesarean delivery in terms of perinatal mortality (excluding malformation), although there was a higher rate of maternal morbidity after Cesarean Section C/S. The delivery of undiagnosed breech at term is even more controversial due to lack of adequate assessment of maternal pelvis and fetal size and normality, which are essential in deciding the mode of delivery.(56)

Breech deliveries have always been topical issues in obstetrics because of the very high perinatal mortality and morbidity. These are due to combination of trauma, birth asphyxia, prematurity and congenital malformation. In addition, 19.4% of neonates undergoing term breech deliveries have long-term morbidity up to the school age irrespective of mode of delivery. Thus wide ranges of management policies have been instituted with the aim of reducing this perinatal morbidity and mortality, and hence improve the quality of life of these infants later in life.(19)

In this stud frequency of undiagnosed breech among Primigravid as presenting in labour was (195/250:78%) while the remaining 55(22%) Primigravid as were diagnosed with breech.

Shafaq Zahoor in his study reported that (80.29%) patients presented with undiagnosed breech and 40(19.71%) had been diagnosed in antenatal clinic.(6) Frequency of undiagnosed breech of this study was almost same to the frequency reported by Shafaqzahoor.

Zainab A. Babayin study showed a low incidence of undiagnosed breech in labor at term(12.9%) compared to 26% and 21% reported lately.(2, 55, 57) However frequency of undiagnosed breech was very high when compared with the results reported by Zainab A. Babay and other studies in the literature.

Ojiyi E from Nigeria in his study reported that there were 122 singleton breech deliveries out of a total 4741 deliveries. The prevalence of singleton term breech deliveries in the study period was 2.6%.(58)H. Alshaheen in his study reported breech presentation among 259/10215(2.54%) deliveries.(7) Ikeanyi Maduabuchi Eugene in his study reported 345(2.6%) singleton breech deliveries among 13,416 deliveries.(59)J. D. Kemfang Ngowa reported incidence of breech delivery at term of 2.98%.(60)

However, most of the studies have reported the breech presentation at term which is also very low as compared to the results of this study. In this study diagnosed breech presentation was seen in 22% primigravid as at term which is quite high however. (22% vs. 2-3%). Short term perinatal outcome sowed that there were only 10(5.1%) neonates with poor APGAR score<7 at 5 minute and only 1(0.5%) neonate was admitted to NICU.

Shafaq Zahoor in his study reported poor APGAR score [$<1/10$ at 5 minutes] among 10(6.13%) neonates. These results are comparable to the results of this study. i.e. [6.13 % vs. 5.1]. As well as none of the neonates were admitted to the NICU. However in this study poor APGAR score at 5 minute was low as that of reported by Shafaq Zahoor.

H. Alshaheen reported poor APGAR score i.e. <7 at 5 minute in 12(5.7%) neonates and 10(4.8%) neonates had admission to NICU.(7) Low APGAR score was almost same as that of study however the admission to NICU was high as that of reported by H. Alshaheen as compared to this study. i.e. (4.8% vs. 0.51%)

Zainab A. Babay in his study reported that frequency of admission in diagnosed and undiagnosed breech group as 9% and 9.3% which is quite high as compared to the results of this study regarding admission to NICU. i.e. 0.51%. (57) She also reported that there was no additional maternal or fetal morbidity in cases of undiagnosed breech. This is also described in literature as this could be partly attributed to the extra care given to the undiagnosed breech in labor.

Ikeanyi Maduabuchi Eugene reported poor APGAR score i.e. <7 at 5 minutes among 72(20.86%) neonates which is quite as that of reported in this study. i.e. 4%(59)J. D. Kemfang Ngowa in his study reported poor APGAR score at 5 minute among 29(11.65%) neonates out of 249 term singleton breech births. These results are almost comparable and similar to the results of this study regarding poor APGAR score. While 30(12.04%) neonates were admitted to NICU which is quite high. In this study only 1(0.51%) neonate was admitted to NICU. (60)

It is believed that the management of term breech in labor, whether diagnosed or undiagnosed, should be made after careful attention to the progress of labor and careful assessment of fetal weight and pelvic adequacy. Prompt surgical intervention should be available to achieve safe delivery of the breech baby as there is no reason to deliver all undiagnosed breeches by C/S.

CONCLUSION:

As per findings of this study high frequency of undiagnosed breech before admission was seen in patients. i.e. 195/250(78%). However prenatal outcome showed that poor Apgar score at 5 minutes was seen in 10(5.1%) neonates and only 1(0.51%) neonate was admitted to NICU. These results can help us to diagnose breech before admission in primigravid as before presenting for their delivery so that timely and accurate decision can be made regarding mode of delivery as well as better perinatal outcome.

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